

Effectiveness of Maitland's Mobilization Versus Sleepers Stretch and Posterior Capsule Stretch on Pain, Rom and Shoulder Functions in Patients with Adhesive Capsulitis: A Randomized Control Trial

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Abstract:

➤ *Background and Objectives:*

Adhesive capsulitis (AC) is a pathological condition of shoulder joint characterized by excessive scar tissue or adhesion formation all across the glenohumeral joint. It is typically marked by a sudden onset of pain and a progressive loss of glenohumeral joint motion, which causes a severe loss of shoulder function. There is a high prevalence in the age group between 40 to 60 years of age. As Compared to men, women are 4 times more likely to be affected by frozen shoulder. AC results in discomfort, pain, stiffness and dysfunction. The study was done to assess the effectiveness of Maitland mobilization vs sleepers and posterior capsule stretch on pain, ROM and shoulder function in patients with adhesive capsulitis.

➤ *Methods:*

According to the sample size estimation the study included 60 participants. All the subjects included were clinically diagnosed by an orthopedic with adhesive capsulitis were screened after finding their suitability as per the inclusion criteria. Participants were briefed about the study and informed consent was obtained for the same. Total of 60 participants were randomly assigned into 2 treatment groups with 30 participants each. Group 1 (n=30) was given Maitland mobilization along with conventional physiotherapy whereas, group 2 (n=30) was followed by vs sleepers and posterior capsule stretch along with conventional physiotherapy protocol. The total duration of treatment was 4 weeks. Pre and post intervention scores were measured in terms of VAS, ROM, and SPADI.

➤ *Outcome Measures:*

Pre and post intervention scores were measured in terms of VAS, ROM, and shoulder disability. The outcome measure pain was measured using Visual analog scale. The availability of range of motion of shoulder was measured using universal goniometer. To calculate the extent of disability caused by the adhesive capsulitis was measured using shoulder pain and disability index.

➤ *Result:*

While comparing pre-test and post-test scores using paired t-test, both the groups showed a significant difference in each parameter (VAS, shoulder ROM, SPADI= <0.001).

Independent sample t-test showed significant improvement in all the parameters (VAS, shoulder ROM in flexion, abduction and external rotation, SPADI= <0.001) of both the groups after 4 weeks of intervention.

➤ *Conclusion:*

On the basis of result obtained from this study, Maitland mobilization is significantly more effective in increasing ROM, reducing pain on VAS and decreasing the shoulder disability compared to sleepers and posterior capsule stretch in patients with adhesive capsulitis.

Keywords: Maitland Mobilization, Adhesive Capsulitis, Visual Analog Scale, Sleepers Stretch, Posterior Capsule, Range of Motion.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Adhesive capsulitis is otherwise also referred to as Frozen Shoulder (FS). It is a frequent pathologic disease of the shoulder joint.¹ Neviaser recommended that adhesive capsulitis was the appropriate name, after discovering persistent inflammation and fibrosis of the joint capsule that was tightly attached to the humeral head during the pathological tests.² It is marked by a sudden onset of pain and a progressive loss of glenohumeral joint motion, which causes a severe loss of shoulder function. It typically begins in one shoulder and frequently affects the other side years after the first shoulder experiences symptoms, although it is uncommon to affect the same shoulder twice.⁶ The condition leads to functional restriction of both active and passive shoulder motion for which radiographs of the glenohumeral joint are essentially unremarkable except for the possible presence of osteopenia or calcific tendonitis.³

The volume of a typical shoulder joint is minimum 15 ml and on an average 20 ml¹⁷. But, the joint volume in a frozen shoulder is usually less than 5 ml. It is well-established that the rotator interval in conjunction with the coracohumeral ligament (CHL) plays a part in the pathophysiologic process of FS and may play crucial role in the development of the condition. The rest of the joint capsule is involved later as the condition progresses.^{18,19,20} There is a high prevalence of frozen shoulder in the age group between 40 to 60 years of age. Although it is uncommon for the same shoulder to reappear, up to 20% of people experience identical issues in their contralateral shoulder.⁵ Within five years, the opposite shoulder begins to deteriorate in 15% of patients and 80 % of patients will experience return of symptoms.^{4,5}

The international Maitland Teachers Association (IMTA) defines the Maitland concept as a process of assessment, examination, and treatment of neuromusculoskeletal disorder by manipulative physiotherapy. The oscillations may have an inhibitory effect on the perception of painful stimuli by repetitively stimulating mechanoreceptors that block nociceptive pathways at the brain stem or spinal cord levels. These movements help improving the nutrition to the cartilage by moving the synovial fluid.

To isolate the soft tissue of the posterior portion of the shoulder, medical professionals and athletes have recently embraced a new stretch technique. Because it is performed with the patient in side-lying position, this technique is also known as the "Sleeper stretch". In order to isolate the posterior soft tissue constraints and conduct the sleeper stretch, scapula is stabilized. Shoulder disorders very commonly involve posterior capsule tightness. The posterior capsule has an important role to play in function and control

of normal arthrokinematics between the humeral head and glenoid cavity. Posterior capsule tightness refers as shortening of the capsule or shortening of the dynamic structures that are attached to this area.

Thus, the study aims to determine the effectiveness of Maitland mobilization versus sleeper stretch and posterior capsule stretch on pain, range of motion and shoulder functions in patients with adhesive capsulitis.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The purpose of study was to evaluate effectiveness of Maitland's mobilization versus sleepers stretch and posterior capsule stretch on pain, rom and shoulder functions in patients with adhesive capsulitis. The study was carried out in Physiotherapy OPD of Narayana Hrudayalaya Health City, Bengaluru.

Total 60 participants were included in the study. The inclusion criterion of the study were Adults aged 40 to 60 years diagnosed with Periarthritis of shoulder, both genders will be included, Global ROM restriction, shoulder pain for more than 3 months, subject with positive abduction and external rotation test and adults who are willing to participate with the symptoms of the adhesive capsulitis. The exclusion criterion included in study were Patients with any trauma or accidental injuries to shoulder, neurological involvement, history or surgery on shoulder, individuals who have intra articular injections to the shoulder joint within 6 months prior to the study, Tumors/malignancy of bone, mental disorders. The study was introduced after screening the subjects according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Written consent was obtained from each participant. 60 subjects were divided into two groups. Group 1 and group 2. The assessment of each group was performed before and after the intervention. The interventions were supported outpatient rehabilitation programs in both groups. Both the groups received conventional physiotherapy treatment followed by Maitland mobilization in group 1 and Sleepers, posterior capsule stretch in group 2.

Conventional physiotherapy treatment includes electrotherapy, finger ladder, pendular exercise, wand exercise. The group 1 received Maitland mobilization along with conventional physiotherapy as mentioned above; anterior glide, posterior glide and caudal glide was given 2 to 3 oscillations per second for 30 seconds, 5 repetitions thrice a week for 4 weeks. The group 2 received sleepers, posterior capsule stretch with 5 repetitions with 30 second hold with 10 sec rest in between each stretch; 5 days a week for 4 weeks. Outcome measures VAS, shoulder ROM and SPADI were assessed pre and post intervention which was for 4 weeks.

III. RESULT

➤ *Age Distribution*

Table 1: The Mean difference of Age in Both the Treatment Groups

	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-Value
AGE	Group-1	51.73	5.078	0.394	0.695
	Group-2	51.20	5.391		

Graph 1: Comparison of Age Distribution Box Plot

- Interpretation: Table no. 1 and graph no. 1 shows distribution of age in group 1 and group 2. Where, the mean age of group 1 is 51.73 ± 5.078 and mean of group 2 is 51.20 ± 5.391 . The P value of age is 0.695 ($t=0.394$).

➤ *Continuous Data*

Table 2: The Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre and Post Test of all the Outcome Measures (VAS, Shoulder Rom and SPADI) in group 1 and group 2

	Group-1		Group-2	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
PAIN PRE	5.50	1.432	5.63	1.520
PAIN-POST	2.57	1.251	3.43	1.478
FLEXION PRE-RANGE OF MOTION	145.60	13.942	145.70	9.675
FLEXION POST-RANGE OF MOTION	166.17	10.674	159.50	9.291
ABDUCTION PRE-RANGE OF MOTION	103.03	11.622	106.33	7.893
ABDUCTION POST-RANGE OF MOTION	151.50	16.874	126.70	10.600
INTERNAL ROTATION PRE	45.43	5.587	44.83	5.272
INTERNAL ROTATION POST	65.47	7.243	63.30	6.814
EXTERNAL ROTATION PRE	17.77	6.004	18.77	5.905
EXTERNAL ROTATION POST	41.00	8.538	26.33	5.054
SPADI PRE	81.27	4.378	82.03	5.136
SPADI POST	57.20	5.524	68.13	5.526

➤ *Comparing between the Group-1 and Group-2*

- *Pain*

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Pain Scores Post-Intervention between Treatment Groups

	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-Value
PAIN-POST	Group-1	2.57	1.251	0.321	0.017*
	Group-2	3.43	1.478		

Graph 2: Comparison of Pain Post Intervention Analysis between Group 1 and 2

- Interpretation: Table no.3 and graph no.2 represents post intervention pain data of both the treatment groups. It is represented by mean and SD values of each group. The mean of group 1 was found to be 2.567 ± 1.251 and group

2 was 3.43 ± 1.478 . The p value for comparison of post intervention pain between the groups was 0.017 ($t=0.321$). This suggests that there is a statistically significant difference in the post-treatment pain values between the two groups.

➤ *Shoulder Rom*

- *Flexion*

Table 4: Comparison of Mean Flexion ROM Post-Intervention between Treatment Groups

	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-Value
FLEXION POST-RANGE OF MOTION	Group-1	166.17	10.674	0.193	0.012*
	Group-2	159.50	9.291		

Graph 3: Comparison of Flexion Rom Post Intervention Analysis between Group 1 and 2.

- Interpretation: Table no.4 and graph no.3 represents post intervention comparison of flexion ROM between both the treatment groups. It is represented by mean and SD values of each group. The mean of group 1 was found to

be 166.17 ± 10.674 and group 2 was 159.50 ± 9.291 . The p value for comparison of post intervention values between the groups was 0.012 ($t=0.193$). This suggests that there is a statistically significant difference in the post-treatment flexion ROM values between group 1 and 2.

➤ Abduction

Table 5: Comparison of Mean Abduction ROM Post-Intervention between Treatment Groups

	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-Value
ABDUCTION POST-RANGE OF MOTION	Group-1	151.50	16.874	0.032	<0.001*
	Group-2	126.70	10.600		

Graph 4: Comparison of Abduction Rom Post Intervention Analysis Between Group 1 and 2

- Interpretation: Table no.5 and graph no.4 represents post intervention comparison of abduction ROM between both the treatment groups. It is represented by mean and SD values of each group. The mean of group 1 was found to

be 151.50 ± 16.874 and group 2 was 126.70 ± 10.6 . The p value for comparison of post intervention pain between the groups was <0.001 ($t=0.032$). This suggests that there is a strong statistically significant difference in the post-treatment abduction ROM values between group 1 and 2.

➤ *Internal Rotation*

Table 6: Comparison of Mean Internal Rotation ROM Post-Intervention between Treatment Groups

	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-Value
INTERNAL ROTATION POST	Group-1	65.47	7.243	0.921	0.238
	Group-2	63.30	6.814		

Graph 5: Comparison of Internal Rotation Rom Post Intervention Analysis Between Group 1 and 2

- Interpretation: Table no.6 and graph no.5 represents post intervention comparison of internal rotation ROM between both the treatment groups. It is represented by mean and SD values of each group. The mean of group 1 was found to be 65.47 ± 7.243 and group 2 was

63.30 ± 6.814 . The p value for comparison of post intervention pain between the groups was 0.238 ($t=0.921$). This suggests there is no statistically significant difference in internal rotation post-treatment between Group 1 and Group 2.

➤ *External Rotation*

Table 7: Comparison of Mean External Rotation ROM post-Intervention Between Treatment Groups

	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-Value
EXTERNAL ROTATION POST	Group-1	41.00	8.538	0.008	$<0.001^*$
	Group-2	26.33	5.054		

Graph 6: Comparison of External Rotation Rom Post Intervention Analysis between Group 1 and 2

- Interpretation: Table no.7 and graph no.6 represents post intervention comparison of external rotation ROM between both the treatment groups. It is represented by mean and SD values of each group. The mean of group 1 was found to be 41 ± 8.538 and group 2 was 26.33 ± 5.054 .

The p value for comparison of post intervention pain between the groups was <0.001 ($t=0.008$). This suggests that there is a strong statistically significant difference in the post-treatment external rotation ROM values between group 1 and 2.

➤ *Shoulder Pain and Disability Index*

Table 8: Comparison of Mean Shoulder Pain and Disability Index (SPADI) Post -Intervention between Treatment Groups

SPADI POST	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-Value
	Group-1	57.20	5.524	0.953	$<0.001^*$
	Group-2	68.13	5.526		

Graph 7: Comparison of Spadi Score Post Intervention Analysis Between Group 1 and 2

- Interpretation: Table no.8 and graph no.7 represents post intervention comparison of SPADI scores between both the treatment groups. It is represented by mean and SD values of each group. The mean of group 1 was found to be 57.20 ± 5.524 and group 2 was 68.13 ± 5.526 . The p

value for comparison of post intervention pain between the groups was <0.001 ($t=0.953$). This suggests that there is a strong statistically significant difference in the post-treatment values between group 1 and 2.

IV. DISCUSSION

Shoulder joint is an exceptional anatomical structure with its remarkable range of motion that it provides. As a matter of fact, it provides highest amount of mobility than any other joint in human body. Therefore, reduced mobility of this joint can lead to severe morbidity.⁵² Adhesive capsulitis is a pathological condition characterized by excessive scar tissue or adhesion formation across the glenohumeral joint. This results in discomfort, pain, stiffness and dysfunction. A painful and stiff shoulder can negatively impact everyday activities and, as a result, degrade quality of life. On the contrary to which there are evidences that prove between 20% and 50% of patients may go on to develop long-lasting symptoms.^{53,54}

According to definition based on American Academy of Orthopaedic Surgeons for diagnosis of adhesive capsulitis diagnosis is made, emphasizing the progressive development of global limitation of shoulder mobility without substantial abnormalities on radiographs.^{55,56} The condition predominantly affects females than males with a ratio of 1.4:1 also, the nondominant hand seems to be affected to a greater extent. Adhesive capsulitis is more common in patients with autoimmune comorbidities, such as diabetes mellitus and thyroid conditions.⁵⁷

The pathophysiology of adhesive capsulitis is unclear. However, current studies suggest primarily there is inflammation present within the synovial lining and joint capsule later reactive fibrosis and adhesions in the synovial lining which triggers Adhesive Capsulitis. Capsular fibrosis and adhesions limit range of motion, and the initial inflammation of the capsule leads to pain.⁶⁰

Pain relief through Maitland's mobilization could be ascribed to an array of beneficial results of mobilization, including of local physiological mechanisms as well as additional central mechanisms. Mechanoreceptors and proprioceptors are stimulated by small oscillations amplitude and distraction movements. As a result of mobilization, oscillation may inhibit the perception of painful stimuli by repeatedly stimulating mechanoreceptors associated to myelinated alpha-beta and alpha-delta fibres at the spinal cord or brain stem level.

The positive impact of engaging in mobility exercises to enhance shoulder function may stem from various factors. One possible explanation is that by performing repeated end-range movements, mechanoreceptors could be stimulated, potentially leading to pain reduction, as suggested by the pain gate theory. Another study demonstrated that exercises trigger the release of non-opioid substances like serotonin, norepinephrine, dopamine, and GABA. Additionally, mobility exercises involve repeatedly moving the joint through its full range of motion, which stretches the joint capsule and consequently enhances the range of motion.⁶³

In a comprehensive analysis done by Cavalleri E et.al where goal was to determine the efficacy of physical therapy in patients with primary or idiopathic frozen shoulder. They

concluded that rehabilitation treatment specifically mobilization and exercises are most effective in treating frozen shoulder. In an investigatory report prepared by Nakandala Piumi et.al the evidence suggests that certain physical therapy techniques and modalities are strongly recommended for pain relief, improvement of ROM, and functional status in patients with adhesive capsulitis. Also, in research done by Tarang K. Jain et.al have determined that: Therapeutic exercises and mobilization are strongly recommended for reducing pain, improving range of motion (ROM) and function in patients with stages 2 and 3 of frozen shoulder.

All the above articles highlight physiotherapy as a vital intervention in the treatment of adhesive capsulitis. Suzie Noten et.al in their investigation to uncover the efficacy of different types of isolated articular mobilization techniques in patients with primary adhesive capsulitis (AC) of the shoulder have shown Maitland technique to be recommended at the moment. In research done by Neeti Mishra et.al on comparing the effectiveness between capsular stretch and sleepers stretch revealed sleepers stretch to be more effective by indicating better outcome results than the other.

So according to previous studies the present study is pursued to evaluate the effectiveness of Maitland's mobilization vs sleepers stretch and posterior capsule stretch on pain, range of motion and shoulder function in patients with adhesive capsulitis.

This current study also found that the selected intervention reduces pain, increases shoulder range of motion, and decreases functional disability, consistent with findings from previous authors.

A. Improvement in Reducing Pain:

In this study pain was measured by visual analog scale. The pre-intervention value for the group 1 and group 2 was 5.50 ± 1.432 and 5.63 ± 1.520 respectively. The post-intervention VAS scores for group 1 & group 2 were 2.57 ± 1.251 and 3.43 ± 1.478 respectively. A paired t-test was performed to calculate significance, demonstrating a significant reduction in pain in both groups post-intervention.

Post-intervention mean values between the two groups were calculated using an independent t-test. A significant difference was found between Group 1 and Group 2 ($p < 0.001$) after 4 weeks of intervention.

In a study performed by Do Moon G et.al evaluated the effect of Maitland mobilization and Kaltenborn mobilization techniques for improving pain and range of motion in patients with frozen shoulders sums up both the type of mobilization is equally effective in improving range of motion and pain. Shehri Abdullah et.al in their study showed Maitland Mobilization along with exercises improves the symptoms of frozen shoulder. Statistical analysis shows that Maitland mobilization is statistically notable in improving the symptoms. Similar results were also found in a study done by Sami S. et.al. Mohammed Ameer Hussain et.al in their study found that sleeper, cross body stretch has statistically

significant better reduction in Pain in VAS in the treatment of frozen shoulder.

B. Improvement in Functional Mobility by Measuring Shoulder Range of Motion:

So, in this current study shoulder range of motion is used to check the functional mobility of patients with adhesive capsulitis and shoulder range of motion is measured using a goniometer. The pre-intervention value for flexion in group 1 and group 2 were 145.60 ± 13.942 and 145.70 ± 9.675 respectively. The post-intervention flexion ROM score for group 1 and group 2 were 166.17 ± 10.674 and 159.50 ± 9.291 respectively. By using paired t-test it is proved that there was significant improvement seen after intervention among the group 1 and group 2.

Now, when compared post-intervention difference value scores between the group 1 and group 2 by using an independent t-test. A significant difference was found in both group 1 and group 2 ($p=0.012$) after 4 weeks of the duration of intervention.

The pre-intervention value for abduction in group 1 and group 2 were 103.03 ± 11.622 and 106.33 ± 7.893 respectively. The post-intervention abduction ROM score for group 1 and group 2 were 151.50 ± 16.874 and 126.70 ± 10.60 respectively. By using paired t-test it is proved that there was significant improvement seen after intervention among the group 1 and group 2.

Now, when compared post-intervention difference value scores between the group 1 and group 2 by using an independent t-test. Significant difference was found in both group 1 and group 2 ($p<0.001$) after 4 weeks of the duration of intervention.

The pre-intervention value for internal rotation in group 1 and group 2 were 45.43 ± 5.587 and 44.83 ± 5.272 respectively. The post-intervention IR ROM score for group 1 and group 2 were 65.47 ± 7.243 and 63.30 ± 6.814 respectively. By using paired t-test it is proved that the significant improvement was not pronounced after intervention among the group 1 and group 2.

Now, when compared post-intervention difference value scores between the group 1 and group 2 by using an independent t-test. There is no statistically significant difference found between both group 1 and group 2 after 4 weeks of the duration of intervention

The pre-intervention value for external rotation in group 1 and group 2 were 17.77 ± 8.538 and 18.77 ± 5.905 respectively. The post-intervention ER ROM score for group 1 and group 2 were 41.00 ± 6.004 and 26.33 ± 5.054 respectively. By using paired t-test it is proved that there was significant improvement seen after intervention among the group 1 and group 2.

Now, when compared post-intervention difference value scores between the group 1 and group 2 by using an independent t-test. So, extremely significant difference was

found in both group 1 and group 2 ($p<0.001$) after 4 weeks of the duration of intervention.

In a study done by Samiksha Sathe et.al concluded there is significant increase in range of motion and better functional outcome when Maitland mobilization therapy along with conventional therapy is given to patients with adhesive capsulitis. Mouleeswari B et.al in their study to find the effectiveness of midlands mobilization and muscle energy technique in adhesive capsulitis patients suggested that there is significant increase in ROM and functional ability as reduced pain by Maitland mobilization in comparison to the latter .

In research done by Duzgun I et.al in the year 2019 in their RCT based on their result suggested that Scapular mobilization and manual posterior capsule stretching interventions were effective in improving the acute joint range of motion in frozen shoulder patients. In a study done by Kedar s et.al have concluded that sleepers stretch is effective in improving shoulder ROM and reducing pain and improves ability to do ADLs.

Range of motion exercises also contribute in improving joint and soft tissue mobility and decreases risk of adhesions and contracture formation. Stretching exercises given were also helpful in breaking the collagen bonds and realignment of the fibres for permanent elongation or increased flexibility and mobility of the soft tissues that have adaptively shortened and become hypo mobile over time in Frozen Shoulder.⁴⁹

C. Improvement in Reducing Functional Disability by using the SPADI Scale:

In this study SPADI scale is used for measuring functional disability with 2 components i.e. pain and disability. The pre-intervention value for the group 1 and group 2 were 81.27 ± 4.378 and 82.03 ± 5.136 respectively. The post-intervention SPADI score for group 1 and group 2 were 57.20 ± 5.524 and 68.13 ± 5.526 respectively. By using paired t-test it is proved that there was significant improvement seen after intervention among the group 1 and group 2.

Now, when compared post-intervention difference value scores between the group 1 and group 2 by using an independent t-test. So, a significant difference was found in both the group 1 and group 2 ($p<0.001$) after 4 weeks of the duration of intervention.

Muhammad Z et.al the findings of their study suggest that Maitland mobilization is effective in decreasing the disability improving the functional status and reducing pain in adhesive capsulitis patients. In research performed by Zaki A et.al in their study revealed that Maitland mobilization not only is effective in reducing pain and improving ROM but also shows significant improvement of the functional scores and associated disability performance. In a study performed by Meena M et.al where they compared effectiveness of Sleeper Stretch and cross-Body stretch For Improving Posterior Shoulder Tightness, Pain and Function in Patients

with Adhesive Capsulitis was performed. This study demonstrated a positive outcome of both the types of stretches for improving the posterior shoulder tightness by improving the range, reducing the pain and enhancing functional level of the patients with adhesive capsulitis.

The rationale behind the improvement in functional independence in both the groups might be due to ease in pain and increased range of motion, consequently lessened suffering in daily activities, pain with specific everyday jobs, and difficulty in lifting and movement of the arm.

Hence, including an exercise program for overall well-being of the patient is essential. The current study demonstrates a combination of Maitland mobilization and sleepers, posterior stretch leads to significant improvement in reducing functional disability.

In this study participants allotted in group 1 were given Maitland mobilization and group 2 were given sleepers and posterior capsule stretch. Both treatments are statistically significant for improvement in reducing pain, increase range of motion and improvement in reducing functional disability in patients with adhesive capsulitis.

V. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the effectiveness in improving movement ability and functional status in both treatment groups are remarkable. However, group 1 (Maitland mobilization + conventional therapy) shows higher significance than group 2 (sleepers stretch and posterior capsule stretch+ conventional therapy).

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